

***Icius hamatus* (C.L. KOCH, 1846) (Araneae: Salticidae) in the Netherlands**

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ABSTRACT. *Icius hamatus* (C.L. KOCH, 1846) (Araneae: Salticidae) in the Netherlands.

This paper presents the first locality of *I. hamatus* in Netherlands. The distribution of this species in Europe is also given and briefly discussed.

KEY WORDS: Araneae, Salticidae, faunistics, new record.

In recent decades, numerous cases of accidental introductions of non-native spider species have been reported across Europe, facilitated by intensive international trade, especially the import of ornamental plants and fruits (NENTWIG & KOBELT 2010, ROZWAŁKA & CZAJA 2021, GIERLASIŃSKI & WRZOŁ 2023). Although many of these records are incidental, some species may establish stable populations in environments with favorable microclimatic conditions and sufficient food supply (ROZWAŁKA & CZAJA 2021). This is supported by their broad ecological tolerance and generally unspecialized predatory habits (MICHALKO *et al.* 2019).

An example of such an introduced species is *Icius hamatus*. This medium-sized jumping spider (family Salticidae), reaching a maximum body length of 6 mm, occurs mainly in North African and southern European countries around the western and central parts of the Mediterranean Basin. In addition, its natural range includes known localities in Portugal, Switzerland, Croatia, Slovenia, Serbia, Albania, Greece, and Turkey (NENTWIG *et al.* 2025).

Icius hamatus inhabits various dry and well-sunlit shrubland environments common in the Mediterranean region, but it can also be found in orchards and gardens (NENTWIG *et al.* 2025, WORLD SPIDER CATALOG 2025). In recent decades, cases of *I. hamatus* being introduced with imported fruit have been recorded in Germany (SCHÄFER & DEEPEN-WIECZOREK 2014), Poland (ROZWAŁKA & CZAJA 2021), and more recently also in the United Kingdom (KILLICK 2023).

Below, a new record of *I. hamatus* from the Netherlands is presented:

– **Breda**, Haagse Beemden, 51°37'17.06"N, 4°45'09.85"E, 1♂, 12.05.2025, outbuildings in a home garden, leg. D. Kojder, det. G. Gierlasiński.

The newly reported locality fits the type of environment in which *Icius hamatus* typically lives. Importantly, less than a kilometre from the new locality, there is a large garden centre, which is likely where the specimen originated. Moreover, some

of the organic waste from this centre is taken to a large composting site located nearby. However, like the records from Poland, Germany, and the United Kingdom, this locality should also be considered incidental. Specimens of this species are likely introduced fairly often into various Central European countries with shipments of fruit (ROZWAŁKA & CZAJA 2021). Nevertheless, *I. hamatus* has high thermal requirements, which may hinder or even prevent the establishment of a stable population. It is possible, however, that under synanthropic conditions, the spider may be able to form small, short-lived populations (ROZWAŁKA & CZAJA 2021, LOGGHE & STEVENS 2025).

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